

VETERINARY SCIENCES

EFICACY OF FLUBENDAZOLE 10% IN POULTRY REARED IN TRADITIONAL SYSTEM

Băcescu B.,

Lecturer, ph.d., Faculty of Veterinary
Medicine Spiru Haret University, Romania

Catrina E.,

Vintilă Brătianu Technological Highschool,
Dragomirești Vale, Ilfov, Romania

Mocanu J.

Veterinary Centre Yogovet, Bucharest, Romania

ABSTRACT

The product has been tested on its effectiveness on flocks of birds reared in a semi-intensive open system, adult chickens, chickens, turkeys, guinea fowls, pheasants diagnosed with syngamosis, heterakiosis, ascaridiosis. The treatment was carried out by administering the product in feed at a dose of 10mg/kg live weight to birds, for 5 days. Helminthological examinations were performed before treatment, 5 days after the treatment and then every 7 days for 27 days. Flubendazole was 95% effective against *Heterakis galline* and *Syngamus trachea* at the control after 5 days and 100% compared to *Ascaridia galli* and *Syngamus trachea* spp. after the control at 12 days after the treatment. In turkey chicks after the first control, infestations with *Syngamus trachea* persisted.

Keywords: Flubendazole, *Ascaridia*, *Heterakis*, syngamosis, necrotic typhlitis.

INTRODUCTION

Current food consumption trends focused upon poultry farms where meat is coming from rearing and feeding conditions close to the biological requirements of birds in recent years make all private breeders more concerned with raising turkeys and guinea fowls in their farms for meat and eggs production. It is known that the guinea fowl egg has a protein content of 13.5% and the vitamin content is 2-3 times higher. Guinea fowl meat has higher nutritional value than beef or chicken because it is richer in protein. Contains the lowest amount of fat, respectively 2.7% in the pulp and 1.1% in the pectoral muscles (Barbat I., 2001). Traditional growth conditions impose poultry exposure to contamination by eating the intermediate hosts or inter-lacing (earthworms, insects, insect larvae) and by eating food or water contaminated with eggs or larvae. This creates a specific profile of nematode infestation, dominated by syngamosis and followed by heterakiosis and ascaridiosis. In the case of guinea fowl were taken as benchmarks studies from African countries (Nigeria, Zimbabwe), where the growth of these birds is much more extensive and climatic conditions are favorable. According to these studies *Ascaridia* infestations occurred in 34% of birds with clinical expression in young individuals accompanied by severe symptoms and significant mortality (Ayeni J.S. et al.).

Flubendazole (Methyl N-[6-(4-fluorobenzoyl)-1H-benzimidazol-2-yl] carbamate) is an antihelminthic from the class of benzimidazole products with a wide range of action against species of nematodes and cestodes observed in chicken, turkey, guinea-fowls and pheasants. It acts by inhibiting the enzymes that coordinate the contraction of the intracytoplasmic microtubule networks and in forming the division spindle in the prophase of the mitotic division.

The product has a low toxicity, the toxic dose in turkeys being 20 times higher than the therapeutic dose;

it has no teratogenic, embryotoxic, cancerigenic or mitogenic activity (Meulder M. 1991). The absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion and residues of Flubendazole have been studied by radioactive marking of the product with C¹⁴. The residues are eliminated from the organism over a longer period, the withdrawal time for the residues being 28 days. The residues are eliminated from the organism over a longer period, the withdrawal time for the residues being 28 days (Tornoe C.).

The purpose of the paper was to determine the efficacy of Rombendazol F powder, in the dose recommended by the manufacturer, to control the parasitic infestations with nematodes and cestodes in growing pigs and in different poultry

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The investigation was conducted on a total of 1,334 poultry specimens reared in household system, assigned to 6 groups according to the species and age: 97 hen chicks, 104 adult hens, 102 turkey chicks, 51 adult turkeys, 50 pheasants and on 104 guinea-fowls reared in a semi-intensive system.

The laboratory investigations conducted with the Mini-Flotac method flotation helminths egg count technique determined the level of helminthic infestation before, and after the treatment with Flubendazole (Rombendazol F 10%) powder.

Mini-FLOTAC is a multivalent technique (i.e., it permits the contemporaneous diagnosis of oocysts and cysts of protozoa, eggs and larvae of nematodes, eggs of trematodes, and cestodes). For this reason, the Mini-FLOTAC are able to reduce time and costs of analysis and compared to other fecal flotation methods showed an overall higher specificity, sensitivity, accuracy, precision, reproducibility, and repeatability for egg identification and incidence. In addition, the Mini-FLOTAC and Fill-FLOTAC are user-friendly devices (i.e., no special equipment such as a centrifuge, or trained technicians are required), so they can be used directly by

veterinarians or farmers in the field (pen-side use). Recently, Rinaldi et al. showed that the use on farm of a portable Mini-FLOTAC-kit (composed of 2 Fill-FLOTAC, 2 Mini-FLOTAC, the salt to prepare the flotation solution and all the material necessary to perform the Mini-FLOTAC technique)

The treatment of helminths – nematodes and cestodes infestations in poultry was done by including the antiparasitic product into the feeds in amounts of 10 mg/kg live weight for 2 consecutive days, while a dose of 5 mg/kg live weight for 2 consecutive days. The post-treatment egg count examination was performed at 5, 12, 19 and 26 days, when the efficacy of the anthelmintic product was assessed. In heavy infestations or clinical, birds were slaughtered and morphopathological examination was performed upon the digestive

tract, followed by histopathological examination after sampling the specific lesions, fixed in neutral formalin saline and further processed for inclusion in paraffin. Paraffin blocks were sectioned at 6 μ(microns), stained preparations were obtained by the trichromatic method of Mallory, examined and microphotographed

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The coproscopic examination conducted on the groups of poultry before the treatment showed infestations with *Ascaridia* sp., *Heterakis* sp. and *Capillaria* sp. in hens and turkey hens, with *Ascaridia*, *Syngamus* and *Capillaria* in the hen and turkey chicks, *Ascaridia*, *Syngamus*, *Heterakis*, *Capillaria* sp. in guinea-fowls and *Ascaridia* and *Syngamus* in pheasants(tab.1)

Tab.1

The incidence of nematodes, the degree of infestation and the therapeutic efficiency

Species and category	Number of treated specimens	Parasitic infestations	Before Treatment Eggs per gram(epg)	5 days	12 days	19 days	29 days
Adult hens	104	<i>Ascaridia</i>	45	15	5	0	0
		<i>Heterakis</i>	40	40	15	5	0
		<i>Capillaria</i>	25	5	0	0	0
Hen chicks	97	<i>Ascaridia</i>	40	10	0	0	0
		<i>Capillaria</i>	20	0	0	0	0
		<i>Syngamus</i>	20	5	0	0	0
Adult turkey hens	51	<i>Ascaridia</i>	10	5	5	0	0
		<i>Capillaria</i>	5	0	0	0	0
Turkey chicks	102	<i>Ascaridia</i>	35	15	0	0	0
		<i>Syngamus</i>	30	15	5	5	0
Guinea-fowls	104	<i>Ascaridia</i>	35	10	5	0	0
		<i>Heterakis</i>	40	10	10	5	0
		<i>Capillaria</i>	15	0	0	0	0
		<i>Syngamus</i>	35	10	10	0	0
Pheasants	50	<i>Ascaridia</i>	30	10	10	0	0
		<i>Heterakis</i>	40	20	10	10	10

It should be mentioned that in semi-intensive growth conditioned by space limiting the access of other species, there is a wide possibility of joint access of several species of birds and joint exposure to sources of contamination. That is why multiple infestations prevailed with the possibility of transmission from one species to another or the contamination of the chicks through access to the breeding spaces for adults(fig.1, fig.2)

Fig. 1 The free-range growth of adult turkeys

Fig. 2 Open-range rearing of turkey chicks

Necropsy examination performed in a total of three adult guinea infested with nematode species, slaughtered at the end of the experiment revealed the presence of *Heterakis gallinae* massive infestations after cutting the intestinal caecums. Infestation was accompanied by typhoid catarrhal, areas of necrosis and ulceration at epithelial level caused by the presence and action of pathogenic products of *Heterakis gallinae* specimens (fig.3, fig.5).

Fig.3 - Massive infestation with *Heterakis* in the cecal lumen

In histological sections made from fragments intestinal caecums infested with *Heterakis gallinae* and killed at the end of the experiment have revealed the following injuries: typhoid catarrh, hemorrhagic typhoid, fatal necrotic epithelial denudation accompanied by lymphohistiocytic infiltration in the chorionic lining (fig.4, fig.6).

Fig.4 - Typhoid intestinal bleeding with epithelial

Fig.5 Massive infestation with *Heterakis cecal hipertrophy*

Fig.6 Larvae of *Heterakis* in chorionic lining of ceca denudation;

CONCLUSIONS

The efficacy of flubendazol(Rombendazol F 10%) powder was 100% five days after treatment in the hen chicks and in the adult hens infested with *Heterakis gallinae*, *Syngamus trachea* and *Capillaria sp.* and twelve days for the infestation with *Ascaridia galli*.

The efficacy was 85 % in adult turkey hens and in turkey chicks, five days after treatment, against the infestations with *Ascaridia*, *Heterakis*, *Syngamus* and *Capillaria*.

The efficacy was 85% in guinea-fowls, pheasants, five days after treatment, against the infestations with *Ascaridia*, *Syngamus* and *Heterakis*

The tolerance of the product during therapy was very good in all investigated

References

1. Meulder Mans W., Hurkmans R., Swiysen E., Heykants J.(1997) – Acomparative study on the excretion and metabolism of flubendazole and mebendazole

in the rat. Unpublished raport V 2940. Submitted to FAO by Janssen Pharmaceutical, Beerce, Belgium.

2. Michiels M., Hendricks R.et all (1983) – Flubendazole residues in eggs and tissues of laying hens. Unpublished raport V 4925. Submitted to FAO by Janssen Pharmaceutical, Beerce, Belgium.

3. Moreno I., Mottier L.et all (2004) – Integrated pharmacological assessment of flubendazole potential for use in sheep: disposition kinetics, live metabolism and parasitic diffusion ability. J. Vet. Pharmacology and therapeutics 27, 299 – 308.

4. Tornoe N., Christensen S.(1991) – Flubendazole residues in hens after treatment with flubendazole medicated food. Unpublished raport. Submitted to FAO by Janssen Pharmaceutical, Beerce, Belgium.

5. Flubendazole Monografie – Institut für Veterinär Pharmakologie und Toxicologie. Winterthurerstrasse 260, 8057 Zürich, Schweiz.